

GENDER IN CONTEMPORARY LINGUISTICS

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the concept of gender in general, the explanation of the concept "gender" by linguistic scientists, its role in the modern cultural life of society.

Today in linguistics, new areas of research into linguistic phenomena are developing very rapidly. Not the least of these linguistic trends is gender studies, which is currently attracting increasing interest. The central concept of gender studies is gender, which is understood as a set of cultural characteristics that determine both the social behaviour of women and men and their relationships with each other.

Gender studies focuses on the cultural and societal factors that determine societal attitudes towards men and women, individual behaviour in relation to gender, stereotypical images of masculinity and femininity - all of which move gender issues from the realm of biology to the realm of social life and culture.

The study of gender in this perspective implies the involvement of data from other sciences. Psycholinguistics, ethno-linguistics, cognitive linguistics, intercultural communication, sociolinguistics and other sciences provide material for linguistic analysis of gender. Gender is considered in linguistics as a cognitive phenomenon manifested both in language clichés and in the features of communicants' speech behaviour.

In her article "Gender Issues in Linguistics", E.I. Goroshko points out that the concept of "gender" entered the modern linguistic paradigm much later than in other humanities, namely in the second half of the last century. Initially, works in this field emerged in the West, and the first systematic descriptions of male and female features of speech were made on the basis of languages from the Germanic and Romance language groups [1].

In contemporary Russian science, there is a great diversity in methodological attitudes in the study of gender, going back to different understandings of its essence, in the discussions of proponents of different approaches to the concept of gender.

One of the signs of strengthening the position of linguistic gender studies as an independent scientific field can be considered the appearance of a number of works of methodological nature, which put the question of gender approach in teaching intercultural communication, consider the problems of developing general scientific approaches to the

study of gender in linguistics, formulate specific scientific tasks of gender aspects of language and communication and the prospects for further scientific research [2].

Gender mainstreaming in science is based on the idea that what matters is not the biological differences between men and women, but the cultural and social significance that society attaches to these differences. What is important is their socio-cultural assessment and interpretation and the construction of power relations on the basis of these differences.

The analysis of the category "gender" allowed us to present the stages of its formation as a term with specific status and structure. Gender reflects a complex socio-cultural process of formation of male and female roles by society and emphasizes differences in behavior, mental and emotional characteristics of a person of one gender or another. The result of this process and its theoretical understanding is also the social concept of "gender". The opposition between "masculine" and "feminine" and the subordination of the feminine to the masculine, which has a long history, are important elements in the creation of gender differences.

Of particular value for our article is the multiplicity of approaches to the definition of gender. Based on the reviewed theoretical material, we have identified the lack of a unified approach to the definition of this term in modern linguistics. Despite the recognition of this term by the majority of researchers and its wide use, there are a number of difficulties arising when reading special literature and related to some differences in the understanding of gender, as well as the comparative novelty of this concept. In this connection, terminological problems of linguistic genderology are being highlighted: the first "Dictionary of Gender Terms" was published, interest in lexicographic problems of gender has increased, which indicates an increase in the level of theoretical development of the new scientific discipline. Nevertheless, scientists note the insufficient development of the methodological base, terminological system, and special methods of gender research.

Furthermore, it should be noted that in defining gender, the author's conceptual position plays a key role first and foremost.

After analyzing the definitions of "gender" proposed by A.V. Kirilina, N. Pushkareva, N. Vorobyeva, G. Brandt, O.A. Voronina, it was decided to use the definition given by A.V. Kirilina as the main one in this article, because we believe that this approach reflects the specifics of the concept of "gender" and also makes it legitimate to study the ideas of masculinity and femininity recorded in the language, which is particularly important for our study.[3]

In the course of the work the possibility of using gender as a text-forming parameter was confirmed, since, according to researchers (O.A. Permyakova, M.V. Garanovich, M.N. Kozhina), subtext correlates with a set of gender features, which allows to study the text in terms of the implementation in it of motivated gender identity of the narrator through female or male gender style.

The theoretical material reviewed and studied during the preparation of this article can be used as a basis for a more detailed consideration of gender differences, which are the basis of many modern linguistic studies, as well as the study of the ways and peculiarities of the manifestation of gender identity of the author in the text.

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